

State of the art review and initial design of 6GSMART extreme KPI mechanisms

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(6GSMART-EZ)

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Acronyms

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5 th Generation
5G-ACIA	5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation
5GC	5G Core
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G	6 th Generation
AF	Application Function
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet Of Things Innovation
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B5G	Beyond 5G
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol
CEI	Cloud-edge-IoT
CNI	Container Network Interface
CORC	Continuum ORChestrator
COTS	Commercial off-the-shelf
CPE	Customer Premise Equipment
CPPSoS	Cyber Physical Production Systems of Systems
CPS	Cyber Physical System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSC	Communication Service Customer
CSP	Communication Service Provider
CU-UP	Centralized Unit – User Plane
CUPS	Control User Plane Separation
CU	Centralised Unit
DL-AoD	Downlink Angle of departure
DL-TDOA	Downlink time difference of arrival
DNN	Data Network Name
DNS	Domain Name System
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End-to-End
E-CID	Enhanced cell ID

ECN	Edge Compute Network
ECOMP	Enhanced Control, Orchestration, Management and Policy
ECS	Amazon Elastic Container Service
EKS	Kubernetes Service
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EUCEI	EU Cloud Edge IoT
FCAPS	Fault, Configuration, Accounting, Performance, and Security
FENS	Factory Edge Network Service
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDC	Google Distributed Cloud
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol (GTP)
GSMA	GSM (Groupe Spéciale Mobile) Association
GW	Gateway
I4.0	Industry 4.0
ICC	Industrial Cloud Continuum
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LKC	Linux Kernel Containers
LoS	Line Of Sight
LST&P	Large Scale Trials and Pilots
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communication
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MOCN	Multi Operator Core Network
MPTCP	Multi-path TCP
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NF	Network Functions
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
NG-RAN	New Generation Radio Access Network
NOP	Network OPERator

NPN	Non-Public Networks
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-standalone
NSaaS	Network Slicing as a Service
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
OAI	Open Air Interface
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh
OGC	Ori Global Cloud
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OP	Operator Platform
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OS	Operating System
OSG	Open-Source Group
OSM	Open-Source MANO
OT	Operational Technology
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
QCI	QoS Class Identifier
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
RT	Real-Time
SA	Standalone
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SCS	Sub Carrier Spacing
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SDO	Standards Developing Organisations
SEP	Service Enablement Platform
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
S-NSSAI	Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
SNS JU	Software Networks & Services Joint Undertaking
SSID	Service Set Identifier
TAC	Tracking Area Code
THz	TeraHertz
TSCTSF	Time Sensitive communication Time Synchronization Function
TSN	Time Sensitive Networking

UE	User Equipment
UL-AoA	Uplink Angle of arrival
UL-TDOA	Uplink time difference of arrival
UN	United Nations
UNICO	Univerzalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication
US	United States
UWB	Ultra Wide Band
VAN	Virtual Application Network
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VM	Virtual Machine
VNS	Virtual Network Services
VPC	Virtual Private Cloud
VPP	Vector Packet Processing
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WAT	Wireless Access Technology
WG	Working Group
XR	Extended Reality

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to deliverable “D1.1.1 - State of the art review and initial design of 6GSMART extreme KPI mechanisms” of the subproject 6GSMART-EZ, “6G for Smart Cyber Physical Production Systems of Systems – extreme KPIs and Zero Touch Automation“, which is devoted to the research on Extreme KPIs and Zero Touch Automation. Particularly, this document presents the contributions from i2CAT to the task devoted to the study and design of solutions aiming at enhancing the KPIs of 5G networks in industrial environments.

The deliverable introduces four main contributions: (i) Wi-Fi MAC mechanisms to enable wireless Time Sensitive Networking (TSN), (ii) High-performance 5G Core User Plane Function (UPF), (iii) Wi-Fi and 5G integration through MultiPath Transport Control Protocol (MPTCP), and (iv) 5GNR-based localisation of AVGs. For each solution, relevant state of the art and initial design is provided, describing the main envisioned steps towards its implementation and evaluation.

1. Introduction

6GSMART is an R&D project under the Spanish UNICO framework that investigates how 5G technology needs to evolve to address the unique needs of presented by Operational Technologies (OT). This deliverable presents the initial work developed within the scope of 6GSMARTEZ subproject, which is devoted to the research on Extreme KPIs and Zero Touch Automation. The goal of this subproject is to develop networking enablers that push forward 5G KPIs in terms of throughput, latency and localization, as well as management enablers that simplify the operations of 5G/6G networks in manufacturing environments.

The adoption of wireless technologies in industrial environments brings evident benefits, mainly related to (i) the reduction of cables, which are costly to deploy and maintain, (ii) the increase of devices density by reducing connectivity barriers, and (iii) enabling device mobility, what allows the emergence of new use cases and applications [1].

In this context, Wi-Fi technologies have prevailed due to its low cost and easy deployment, based on the utilization of unlicensed ISM bands, the maturity and high commercial availability of Wi-Fi Access Points (APs) and user equipment (UE), and the continuous enhancement of capabilities through the new versions of the IEEE 802.11 standard adopted by the Wi-Fi Alliance in the different Wi-Fi generations [2]. Nevertheless, Wi-Fi presents some performance issues when increasing the distance between the stations and the UEs, and, although coverage can be extended by increasing the number of APs, handovers can lead to service interruption [3]. Additionally, compared to cellular networks, it lacks mechanisms to effectively enable QoS guarantees and support URLLC traffic [1].

To tackle these challenges, 5G Non-Public Networks (NPNs) have emerged as a proper solution. In addition to the common features of cellular networks, such as reliability, security, or mobility management, 5G RAN covers by design some of the most demanded industrial requirements, like private coverage and access network, flexible resource allocation or customized service according tailored to the use case demands [1]. Related to the latter, network slicing, edge computing and 5G NR based localisation technologies are of special interest to reach the required Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Additionally, 5G architecture supports integration with non-3GPP technologies, such as Wi-Fi, and the integration with Time Sensitive Networking, which are very relevant in industrial scenarios.

In this context, this deliverable introduces the state of the art and the initial design related to the solutions to provide extreme KPIs in 6GSMART-EZ being studied and developed by i2CAT. In particular, the main focus is on mechanisms related to the Radio Access Network (RAN), also including the Wi-Fi technology due to its widespread deployment in industrial scenarios, and on solutions using 5G NR to enhance the localisation of Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs).

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents a brief review on 5G, beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G KPIs, with special focus on industrial use cases and URLLC.

- Section 3 reports relevant state of the art and the initial design of the different solutions being studied and developed by i2CAT within the scope of this subproject: Wi-Fi MAC mechanisms to enable wireless Time Sensitive Networking (TSN), High-performance 5G Core User Plane Function (UPF), Wi-Fi and 5G integration through MultiPath Transport Control Protocol (MPTCP), and 5G NR-based localisation of AVGs.
- Section 4 concludes the deliverable by summarizing its main topics and expounding future work in the related tasks.

2. Beyond 5G/6G extreme KPIs in industrial environments

5G targeted specific values for standard network KPIs, strongly related to the three fundamental 5G service categories: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC), and Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC). Figure 2-1 summarizes 5G service categories, related uses cases and targeted KPIs.

Summary of 5G Use Cases

Figure 2-1: Summary of 5G Use Cases and expected KPIs - Source: <https://www.5gworldpro.com/blog/2019/05/28/84-summary-of-5g-use-cases/>

In Industry 5.0, main emphasis has been devoted to URLLC category [1], since industrial applications usually require of high reliability, low latency, and very low packet error rate. For instance, URLLC capabilities are key to match TSN features and requirements, such as synchronized or deterministic connectivity. In [4], the 5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation (5G-ACIA), describes targeted uses cases and their required 5G functions, services and KPIs, which are summarized in Table 2-1. Similarly, 3GPP TS 22.104 addresses Service requirements for cyber-physical control applications in vertical domains [5], also providing an extensive list of performance requirements.

Table 2-1: Industry KPIs and targeted values [4]

Type/KPI	Example/Targeted Value
Data traffic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodic deterministic communication • Aperiodic deterministic communication • Non-deterministic communication • Mixed traffic
End-to-end latency	0.5 ms to 500 ms
Data rate	Up to several Gbit/s
Time synchronicity	Down to 1 us
Availability	99.9% to 99.999999%
Positioning	Between 0.2 m and 10 m

Note that both reports also consider positioning KPI, since high accuracy positioning is becoming essential in Industry to track mobile devices like AGVs. Indeed, as shown in Figure 2-2, relevant industrial UCs may require features from different service categories. For instance, since, as illustrated in Table 2-1, different types of traffic need to be considered to cover all industrial applications, the data rate KPI could be also relevant (e.g., video streaming-based applications).

Figure 2-2: Overview of industrial use cases according to 5G service categories [6].

In the context of the URLLC category, the different 5G releases have bring new features and enhancements, aiming to satisfy the latency and reliability requirements of applications. In the following list we briefly describe the main features of each 5G release regarding URLLC support [7], also including some details on positioning-related mechanisms [8]:

- **Release 15:** Release 15 was the initial 5G release, introducing several 5G native features relevant to URLLC. First, at the core network side, edge computing allows to execute services close to the RAN, thus reducing end-to-end latency and impact of transport networks. Additionally, 5G introduced new QoS Class Identifier (QCI) support, called 5QI, to handle the QoS of new categories such as URLLC on a per-bearer basis. At the radio level, flexible Sub Carrier Spacing (SCS) were introducing, allowing to decrease the time length of symbols. Also, mini-slots were introduced for shorter packet transmission duration without requiring to use the full length slot. Additional functionalities were incorporated into the radio interface design to minimize latency, including regular monitoring of PDCCH, often occurring more than once per slot in typical scenarios, or the utilization of specific PUCCH formats. Regarding positioning, some basic features were introduced according to the non-standalone (NSA) deployment case (e.g., using LTE carriers for positioning) and radio access technology (RAT)-independent deployment (i.e., non-NR-based methods such as GNSS or Wi-Fi).
- **Release 16:** At the core network level, redundant transmission was introduced for high-reliability communication, allowing to duplicate user packets through two disjoint user plane paths. Regarding the radio interface, enhancements were made to the Physical Layer to facilitate the support of URLLC in various ways: introduction of new DCI formats, improved PDCCH monitoring capability, sub-slot based HARQ-ACK feedback, enhancements to PUSCH, improved inter-UE transmission prioritization and multiplexing, and the introduction of multiple active configured grant configurations for a BWP. RAT-dependent positioning techniques based on NR were introduced in this release: NR Enhanced cell ID (E-CID), Downlink time difference of arrival (DL-TDOA), Uplink time difference of arrival (UL-TDOA), Downlink Angle of departure (DL-AoD), Uplink Angle of arrival (UL-AoA) and Multi-cell round trip time (multi-RTT). These techniques use measurements at the UE and/or network side, which can be reported to a centre location to compute the location or, in the case of downlink techniques, can be conducted by the UE.
- **Release 17:** One of the main contributions of release 17 was to harmonize features of unlicensed spectrum and URLLC, which was mainly focused on licensed spectrum in previous releases. Also, edge relocation was enabled, allowing to reallocate edge according to latency requirements. Other enhancements were included in the feature “Enhanced Industrial IoT and URLLC support for NR”. For instance, support for time synchronization and time sensitiveness was expanded by enabling Application Functions (AF) to interface the Time Sensitive communication Time Synchronization Function (TSCTSF) in order to provide the requirements for QoS, traffic characteristics for QoS scheduling optimization, or time synchronization activation and deactivation. Positioning enhancements were also mainly devoted to the industrial IoT and URLLC scenario, targeting 20-30 cm location accuracy in indoors and 100 ms of maximum latency when determining the location.

Starting from release 18, 5G Advanced will kick off the path to 6G, introducing beyond 5G (B5G) features [9]. Release 18 is focused on some transversal features, such as AI/ML support or energy efficiency, and on addressing specific requirements from operators and verticals, such as Extended Reality support or Non-terrestrial networks

integration. Enhancements to eMBB and URLLC, and its application to industrial IoT will be also considered. Additionally, support for deterministic networking is being studied.

Two flagship European projects, Hexa-X and its continuation Hexa-X-II, are leading the way to the design of next generation 6G wireless networks. In deliverable D1.3 [10], Hexa-X reports envisioned KPIs for future UCs in industrial scenarios, which can be summarized as follows:

- **Digital Twins for manufacturing:** In the context of manufacturing scenarios, Digital Twins, which are virtual replicas of physical assets or processes, can enable real-time and accurate 4D (space and time) digital representation of the industrial manufacturing environment. This imposes extreme latency and reliability constraints for the communication between the physical world and the digital twin. Additionally, throughput should be high enough to support this communication for a massive number of physical devices. Table summarizes some of the envisioned KPIs for this use case.

Table 2-2: Digital Twins for manufacturing KPIs [10].

Type/KPI	Example/Targeted Value
UE density	Up to 100 UEs over a service area of 50m x 10m x 10m (length x breadth x height)
UE mobility	Mix of static and mobile UEs
End-to-end latency	0.1 ms to 100 ms
Data rate	Peak: 10 – 100 Gbps, Average: 1 – 10 Gbps
Availability/Reliability	99.9% to 99.999999%
Positioning	cm-level, 10-1000 ms latency

- **Interacting & cooperative mobile robots & flexible manufacturing:** This use case involves flexible indoor manufacturing, emphasizing direct interaction among robots on a factory floor to achieve shared objectives like production tasks. Human involvement varies, sometimes being necessary for interactions. Examples include multiple robots coordinating precise movements in modular production cells, robots assisting fixed machines, humans engaging with machinery or robots either indirectly through sensing systems or directly through interfaces, and robots learning from human interaction to improve task execution and error handling.

Table 2-3: Interacting & cooperative mobile robots & flexible manufacturing KPIs [10].

Type/KPI	Example/Targeted Value
UE density	Predominant machine-to-machine communication between robots, AGVs, and static machinery (density: ~1 per sqm), for collaborating robots up to 5 per sqm
UE mobility	Mobile robots / AGVs with movement speed <10 m/s
End-to-end latency	0.5 ms to 25 ms
Data rate	< 0.1 Mbps for control
Availability/Reliability	99.9999% / up to 99.9999999%
Positioning	0.01 – 0.05 m, 0.1-100 ms latency

Regarding Hexa-X-II, Deliverable D1.2 [11] leverages Hexa-X results to present or redefine new use cases and KPIs that can be related to industrial scenarios. Hexa-X-II also introduces sustainability, environmental, social and economic analysis for each use case. UCs and required KPIs are summarized as follows:

- **Realtime Digital Twins:** As in the Hexa-X case, the realtime digital twin deals with precise digital representation of real-world entities, encompassing processes, products, individuals, and functionalities found in various domains such as industry, smart cities, or construction. This digital twin relies on network connectivity to gather data from diverse sources like databases, sensors, tags, and data models, and can optionally influence real-world systems through feedback loops. Dedicated software, often incorporating specialized AI/ML algorithms, aggregates, generates, and visualizes the digital twin, while the low-latency capabilities of 6G networks enable real-time interactions and even direct control over physical processes. Main challenges are to increase production quality and efficiency, prevent situations where humans are put at risk by being physically present in unsafe environments, guaranty the privacy and trustworthiness, and enable accessibility of DT models.

Type/KPI	Example/Targeted Value
UE density	1-10 per sqm
UE mobility	< 100 km/h
End-to-end latency	Order of ms
Data rate	< 100 Mbps
Reliability	99.99999%
Positioning	< 10 cm

Table 2-4: Realtime Digital Twins KPIs [11].

- **Cooperating Mobile Robots:** This use case focus on autonomous robots possessing mobility, environmental sensing capabilities, and the capacity to

execute productive tasks. These robots engage in communication with each other, other machines, and nearby humans to fulfill individual tasks contributing to a collective objective. Communication serves the purposes of safety and cooperation, allowing groups of robots to undertake tasks beyond their individual capabilities and enabling individual robots to perceive their environment more comprehensively. Emphasizing local ad hoc connectivity within private networks, this use case envisions scenarios spanning industrial manufacturing campuses, construction sites, and smart living environments. Main challenges include understanding and addressing the communication requirements of machines in the future, using limited resources efficiently (materials, energy, and human effort), adapting to dynamic requirements of the market, end-user access to custom manufacturing, and safe and trustworthy interactions with tools that can make decisions.

Table 2-5: Cooperative mobile robots KPIs [11].

Type/KPI	Example/Targeted Value
UE density	< 0.1 per sqm
UE mobility	< 20 km/h
End-to-end latency	< 0.8 ms
Data rate	< 10 Mbps
Reliability	99.999% - 99.99999%
Positioning	< 0.1 m (fine), < 1 m (coarse)

At the technological level, both projects aim at advancing on similar enablers to provide the envisioned KPIs: integration of AI in the RAN and the air interface, adoption of THz communications, Distributed MIMO or joint communication and sensing approaches.

3. Extreme KPIs mechanisms

This section introduces the main mechanisms being studied, evaluated, developed and/or integrated within the scope of the 6GSMART-EZ project in order to contribute to the provision of extreme KPIs in industrial environments. Two main topics are contemplated: RAN related mechanisms and localisation mechanisms.

2.1 Radio Access Network Mechanisms

Three different approaches are considered under the umbrella of RAN mechanisms: Wi-Fi MAC mechanisms to enable wireless Time Sensitive Networking (TSN), High-performance 5G Core User Plane Function (UPF) and Wi-Fi and 5G integration through MultiPath Transport Control Protocol (MPTCP). All the three approaches are very relevant and applicable in industrial scenarios in order to provide extreme KPIs using technologies that are already being considered in real scenarios and, therefore, in other tasks of this project: 5G Non-Public Networks (NPN), Wi-Fi and TSN.

2.1.1 Wi-Fi MAC mechanisms to enable wireless TSN

Multi-Link Operation (MLO) is a new MAC feature in Wi-Fi 7 that plays a pivotal role in enhancing Wi-Fi determinism by simultaneously leveraging multiple links, thereby reducing latency. Furthermore, MLO contributes to heightened reliability through the duplication of packets across various links, and the aggregation of multiple links results in a noteworthy boost in overall throughput. These characteristics collectively position the multilink feature as a compelling solution for addressing the stringent determinism needs in industrial applications. The key component that determines the performance of MLO is a scheduler function that decides how MAC Protocol Data Units (MPDUs) coming from the upper layers need to be forwarded through each of the links that belong to the MLO. Next, we survey state of the art in MLO scheduling.

2.1.1.1 State of the art

Various techniques have been investigated by researchers to implement multilink scheduling in IEEE 802.11be networks. The primary objective is to enhance the latency, reliability, and throughput of time-critical data.

We categorized MLO schedulers in the state of the art into two main groups, namely static and dynamic. In the static approach, the scheduling criteria remains fixed throughout the network's lifetime. Conversely, in a dynamic approach, the scheduling undergoes dynamic changes over time.

Static schedulers encompass Load Balancing (LB) [12], which involves distributing the load among available links, Packet duplication (PD) for duplicating the same packet on multiple links to enhance reliability, and Packet Splitting (PS), which involves dividing packets into smaller chunks and transmitting them through multiple links. In [13], the authors introduce channel segregation as a static approach, which involves two distinct strategies: a dedicated channel for both data and signalling and a separate channel specifically designated for time-critical data. For scenarios with strict latency requirements and large or intermediate-sized packets, defining separate signalling and data channels would be a more effective strategy. A dedicated separate channel can be

used for long transmissions with strict latency requirements. The latter approach can be extended to further subdivide the dedicated channel into smaller sub-channels, providing a means to manage intensive traffic characterized by small-sized packets. In [14], authors used a packet-splitting mechanism to transmit packets and, when a chunk is missing it retransmits using all available links, hence suggesting it can mitigate the adverse impact of transmission failure on system performance.

In the dynamic approach, the scheduler adapts link-selection policies using local information available at the STA or global (network-wide) information. In [15], authors proposed a scheduler for improving reliability and latency for industrial cyclic traffic by introducing a hybrid approach that selects links by applying PD, PS or LB according to global information. In [16], the authors compared different policies that are updated based on the link congestion metric. These policies include the Least Congestion Control (LCC), as well as both static and dynamic load balancing approaches that consider the congestion level at each link, namely Congestion-aware Load Balancing (CALB). The authors performed simulations considering controlled and uncontrolled traffic scenarios. They concluded that LCC performs well in a controlled environment, while CALB performs better in uncontrolled and dense scenarios. However, note that these policies were fixed for the entire life of a flow. In [17], the same authors extended their work and suggested that the above policies can be further improved in terms of latency if they are adapted dynamically.

Machine learning techniques have also been applied to investigate multilink scheduling. In [18], the MH-RSAC, a RL algorithm for traffic distribution, is introduced. Comparative analysis against non-RL baselines, LCC and LB, highlights MH-RSAC's superiority, with improvements of 6% to 35.2% in TDR when compared with other dynamic schedulers.

Despite the potential of this innovative technology in diverse settings, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding the practical application of IEEE 802.11be's MLO in industrial and factory-like environments. Specifically, there is a lack of proposals that comprehensively study MLO in scenarios involving multiple flows with varying requirements or SLAs, which are common in industrial environment. For instance, a collaborative robot may require a tight delay bound of 5 ms [19], while a human-machine interface (H2M) may have a relaxed delay bound of 50-200 ms [20]. Therefore, a different approach is needed to cater to the specific requirements imposed by different traffic flows. It is worth noting here that MLO schedulers proposed in the literature do not explicitly define an SLA, i.e. they try to improve performance in a best-effort or greedy way. This approach may be ineffective for addressing both stringent and flexible SLAs simultaneously. The greedy nature of flexible SLAs could adversely affect the stringent ones, leading to suboptimal performance and challenges in meeting their SLAs. A more nuanced and adaptive strategy is needed to concurrently address the varying demands of stringent and flexible SLAs.

2.1.1.2 Initial design

In this section we describe the system model that will be used in 6GSMART to design an MLO scheduler that can enforce SLAs, as it is required in industrial environments. We will then also provide an exact definition for how per-flow SLAs will be computed. The detailed MLO scheduler design will however be left for the next deliverable.

Figure 3-1 depicts the system model considered in this study. The configuration includes two types of STAs and a multilink-enabled AP:

- Background STAs: these are operated as background STAs, generating non-SLA flows (non time-critical) on legacy devices with single-link connections. The purpose of these STAs is to create interference. In Figure 3-1, STA1 to STA3 are background one.
- SLA-based STAs: these are Multi-Link Devices STAs (MLD-STAs) and are responsible for transmitting a diverse set F of flows, each denoted as $f \in F$, and associated with its specific SLA (such as delay bound and allowed percentage of SLA breach). In the Figure 3-1 production line and collaborative robots are using MLD-STAs for transmitting flows to MLD-AP.

Notice that all MLD STAs in Figure 3-1 are assumed to be STR (Simultaneous Transmit and Receive) capable, hence Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Congestion Avoidance (CSMA/CA) rules are applied to all their links independently. The lower part of Figure 3-1 depicts the internal architecture of an MLD device. The process starts when MLD STA's MAC receives packets from the upper layers. Those packets are then classified according to the flow $f \in F$ they belong to. Based on the SLA for that flow, the scheduler forwards the packet to link $i \in L$ according to a probability $P(f,i)$. The job of our scheduler, which we refer to as SLA-MLO, is to determine $P(f,i)$ for each flow and link in a dynamic way.

Figure 3-1: Network Model considered for this work. STA1 to STA3 represent legacy devices with single-link capabilities, while the production line and collaborative robots are equipped with multilink capabilities, featuring SLA flows.

We next discuss the SLA model that will be used to design SLA-MLO. In industrial applications, the timing of data and control signal flows is often synchronized with the cycle time of the manufacturing process. Thus, latency is a critical factor that affects the performance and efficiency of the process. Cycle times can vary widely from less than 1 ms for field bus communications to several hundred milliseconds for controllers to the edge communication [20].

Defining SLAs exclusively in terms of strict delay bounds, is not practical in unlicensed and contention-based access technologies such as Wi-Fi, where interference is hard to control even in industrial environments. Therefore, we adopt a more flexible notion of SLA based on the triple (DTH_f, ErrorTH_f, T_{SLA}), where:

- DTH_f: indicates the maximum allowed delay from the moment a packet from flow *f* is received from the ingress queue until it is successfully acknowledged (c.f. Figure 3-1).
- ErrorTH_f: indicates the percentage of packets of flow *f* that are allowed to exceed DTH_f.
- T_{SLA}: indicates the duration of a running time window within which the percentage of packets of flow *f* exceeding DTH_f has to be kept below ErrorTH_f.

Based on this definition of SLA, we can assess the level of SLA compliance of a flow in the following way. First, a MLD STA measures the percentage of packets with a delay above DTH_f for each flow *f* every *t* sample, resulting in a time varying signal Error_f(*t*). To check whether this error signal is compliant with the SLA, we first compute the moving average of Error_f(*t*) within a window of duration T_{SLA}, which can be computed using a convolution operation:

$$\text{Avg_error_f}(t) = \text{Error_f}(t) * \left(\frac{1}{T_{SLA}} \right) \text{Sq}(t)$$

Where Sq(*t*) is a square signal of duration T_{SLA} seconds. Then, the SLA deviation for flow *f* can be derived in the following way:

$$\text{SLA_dev_f}(t) = \max(\text{Avg_error_f}(t) - \text{Error_TH}_f, 0)$$

Note that SLA_{dev}_f(*t*) is only increased when flow *f* exceeds its SLA's error threshold and is not decreased when the flow stays below the error, as this does not bring gains from the application perspective. Finally, the average SLA deviation across all flows is obtained as:

$$\frac{1}{|F|} \sum_{f \in F} \text{SLA_dev_f}(t).$$

2.1.2 High-performance UPF

One of the key advancements in 5G networks is their ability to cater to the specific needs of various industries through customized radio access, core, and transport networks. These networks are designed to be adaptable to the requirements of vertical services, necessitating a flexible and cloud-native network architecture. This feat was accomplished within the 5G Core through the adoption of the Service Based Architecture (SBA) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) paradigms [21]. SBA facilitates the dynamic deployment and interconnection of Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) such as the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), the Session Management Function (SMF), and the User Plane Function (UPF), which might be deployed in different environments (e.g., cloud and edge

The softwarisation and virtualisation of network functions have emerged as fundamental technological foundations of 5G [22]. This significance is poised to further amplify in Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G networks, which aspire to embrace a fully cloud-native architecture [23]. By implementing network functions as VNFs, essential functionalities like network slicing, control-user plane separation (CUPS), edge computing, and disaggregated virtual Radio Access Network (vRAN) are enabled, thereby enhancing the adaptability of the network to meet specific service requirements and dynamic changes. Main examples of such functions include the 5G Core User Plane Function (UPF) and the Centralized Unit - User Plane (CU-UP). Although virtualization allows these user-plane functions to operate on general-purpose IT or Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) servers, this approach entails certain challenges in terms of performance due to the capabilities of the COTS servers (e.g., in terms of CPU and interfaces) and the UPF implementation (e.g., open-source implementations).

To this end, this section presents the state of the art and the initial design of the work related to the evaluation of high-performance UPFs and its integration within the 6GSMART solution.

2.1.2.1 State of the art

In recent years, softwarisation has fuelled the emergence and availability of 5G Core solutions, which can run on top of COTS equipment. Particularly, open-source implementations are of special interest in this project due to minimise dependence on a particular vendor and facilitate the introduction of new features developed by the community (for instance, new 3GPP releases). Follows a list of the main implementations of the state of the art, detailing its main features [24]:

- Open5Gs¹: Open5Gs is an open-source implementation of the 5G Core (Release 17) which supports required functionalities such as slicing, SBA, NFV, CUPS and MOCN. It also allows a flexible configuration of the different NFs through YAML files. Figure 3-2 shows the hybrid architecture of Open5Gs, which supports 4G (LTE, 5G NSA) and 5G SA deployments. As depicted in the figure, the User Plane (i.e., UPF in 5G SA) can be deployed in a different server, for instance in an edge server located near the RAN nodes to enable extreme KPIS in industrial environments. Additionally, Open5Gs allows to specify UPF selection policies based on slicing or data network criteria.

¹ <https://open5gs.org/>

Figure 3-2: Open5Gs architecture (source: Open5Gs website)

- Free5GC²: Free5GC is an open-source 5G core network implementation compliant with 3GPP standards (Release 15), featuring modular architecture for easy customization and extension through the support of SBA. It supports features such as CUPS, slicing and integration of non-3GPP technologies. It was adopted by the Open Networking Foundation (ONF) to develop SD-CORE project together with ONF's 4G OMEC core³. Figure 3-3 depicts the main architecture of SD-Core, which has a notable emphasis on APIs for subscriber management. Additionally, it implements different UPF solutions allowing data plane acceleration through hardware or software solution such as Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK), or programmability through P4.

² <https://free5gc.org/>

³ <https://opennetworking.org/sd-core/>

Figure 3-3: SD-Core architecture (source: SD-Core website)

- Magma⁴: Another relevant initiative, in this case part of the Linux Foundation and Facebook connectivity, is Magma. As illustrated in Figure 3-4, it implements a hybrid 4G and 5G Core, release 16 compliant, which also allows to incorporate Wi-Fi networks through a specific Access Gateway. This element, encompasses the control and data plane of the different access networks (e.g., implements the Evolved Packet Core (EPC) in 4G or the 5G Core NFs in 5G SA). Additionally, the Federation Gateway allows the integration with operators' mobile cores. Finally, the Orchestrator implements configuration and monitoring of the wireless network.

Figure 3-4: Magma Core architecture (source: Magma webpage)

⁴ <https://magmacore.org/>

- Open Air Interface (OAI)⁵: The 5G Core implementation of Open Air Interface also supports the SBA architecture and is compliant with release 16. Its development is based on iterative releases, which incorporate new features or NFs. For instance, last release incorporated Network Exposure Function (NEF) and Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) functions⁶. Its main architecture is detailed in Figure 3-5. Regarding the user plane, it provides a UPF based on Vector Packet Processing (VPP) with Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) support.

Figure 3-5: OAI 5G Core (source: OAI webpage)

As has been exposed, there are several alternatives for the 5G Core, being all of them suitable for the requirements of this project. Therefore, we have selected Open5Gs as our baseline 5G Core for 6GSMART, since we have integrated it in several projects before, leading to a notable performance, stability, and compatibility with several RAN vendors. Additionally, it has been also selected by the companies in charge of the TSN and multi-RAT tasks, which reported also experience on using it.

Nevertheless, the main focus of this task is to select, characterize and evaluate an UPF implementation with the objective of providing extreme KPI. From our previous experience using Open5Gs, we found that its UPF has some issues to provide high performance in COTS servers (e.g., a throughput higher than 1 Gbps), since its implementation is single-threaded and uses TUN virtual interfaces. Similar conclusions have been reported by the community using Open5Gs⁷, also regarding latency and

⁵ <https://openairinterface.org/oai-5g-core-network-project/>

⁶ <https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/cn5g/oai-cn5g-nwdaf>

⁷ https://github.com/s5uishida/simple_measurement_of_upf_performance?tab=readme-ov-file#results

packet losses, leading to the adoption of solutions based on VPP and DPDK, such as OAI's UPF-VPP⁸.

VPP is a well-known Vector Packet Processing technology, currently released under FD.io⁹ framework, which allows high-speed packet processing in user-space. VPP processes vector of packets instead of individual packets, thus increasing performance and leading to stable throughput and latency. Additionally, the DPDK framework allows to bypass the traditional Linux kernel-based forwarding scheme, which leads to poor performance due to hardware interrupts, device IO processing by the kernel and data copying between kernel and user space [25]. DPDK it's a poll mode driver for the NICs, which constantly picks up packets, this way increasing performance by not relying on interruptions. VPP then leverages DPDK to process and forward packets efficiently at the user plane. This way, in the case of the UPF, packets are forwarded very fast from the N3 interface (user plane) to the N6 interface (data plane), and vice versa [25].

Figure 3-6: DPDK packet processing – Source: <https://www.gadgeon.com/blog/vpp-for-data-plane-developers-an-introduction/>

Note that this approach is very appropriate for UPFs hosted in COTS servers, since this way they can dedicate the CPU processing power to packet processing and forwarding, maximizing its performance. For example, in [26] authors compare different UPF acceleration technologies and their impact on latency for URLLC traffic, finding that DPDK offers a notable performance for software-based technologies, achieve soft real-time capable GTP en- and decapsulation.

2.1.2.2 Initial design

We have selected Open5GS control plane and OAI's VPP-UPF as the basis of our solution. We are currently benchmarking the performance of VPP-UPF, comparing it with the vanilla version of Open5GS. The benchmark is based on the following scenario, illustrated in Figure 3-7:

⁸ <https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/cn5g/oai-cn5g-upf-vpp>

⁹ <https://fd.io/>

Figure 3-7: High-performance UPF scenario.

- **UPF server:** The UPF server hosts the UPF implementation (bare metal deployment). As aforementioned, we plan to benchmark Open5GS and VPP- implementations, comparing its performance. It interfaces the Data Plane Server through the N6 interface (10 Gbps, direct link), the 5G Core Control Plane (SMF) through the N4 interface (10 Gbps, via switch) and the RAN nodes through the N2 interface (10 Gbps, via switch). The server is a Supermicro SuperServer E302-9D, with a Intel® Xeon® processor D-2123IT (4 cores, 8 threads), 32 GB of RAM, and 2x 10G SFP+ ports, 2x 10GBase-T LAN ports and 4x 1GbE LAN ports.
- **5G Core Control Plane server:** It hosts the NFs comprehending the 5G Core Control Plane, using the Open5GS solution, interfacing the UPF through the SMF (N4, 10 Gbps, via switch) and the RAN nodes through the AMF (N2, 10 Gbps, via switch). The server is an Intel NUC NUC10i7FNH, with a Intel Core i7-10710U 1.10 - 4.70 GHz (6 cores, 12 threads), 64 GB of RAM, and a 10 Gbps port through a thunderbolt adapter.
- **Data plane server:** Its hosts the data plane, which will be used basically to benchmark the performance of the UPF (e.g., by using Iperf tool¹⁰). It interfaces the UPF through the N6 interface (10 Gbps, direct link). The server is an Intel NUC NUC10i7FNH, with an Intel Core i7-10710U 4.70 GHz (6 cores, 12 threads), 64 GB of RAM, and a 10 Gbps port through a thunderbolt adapter.
- **RAN emulator servers 1 and 2:** It host the RAN emulator, which is based on PacketRusher software¹¹. PacketRusher, which leverages my5G-RANTester¹² and uses libraries from the free5GC project, is able to simulate multiple UEs (up 10K) and a gNB, by supporting N1 (NAS), N2 (NGAP) and N6 (GTU-U) interfaces. Compared to other emulation solutions such as my5G-RANTester or UERANSIM¹³, it allows to reach significant higher data rates using the GTP-U interface (5 GB/s per UE, according to the specifications). In some initial tests, we have reached around 5 Gbps using iperf3 (TCP). The server is an Intel NUC NUC6i7KYK, with a Intel Core i7-6770HQ 3.5 GHz (4 cores, 8 threads), 32 GB

¹⁰ <https://iperf.fr/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/HewlettPackard/PacketRusher>

¹² <https://github.com/my5G/my5G-RANTester>

¹³ <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>

of RAM, and a 10 Gbps port through a thunderbolt adapter. If needed, additional servers will be added to reach higher aggregated throughputs.

- **Switch:** Edgecore enterprise switch AS4610-54P. It is a high-performance Gigabit Ethernet Layer 3 switch featuring 54 ports; with 48 10/100/1000BASE-T ports, 4 x 10G SFP+ uplink ports, and 2 x 20G QSFP+ stacking ports.

Regarding the KPIs, we will analyse the main indicators relevant to the UPF performance in industrial scenarios: throughput, latency, and reliability. In addition, we will consider the energy related KPIs, such as the CPU and energy power consumption, to derive energy efficiency. Finally, we will also contemplate integrating the testbed with a real RAN. Although this will limit the peak throughput due to radio constraints (i.e., bandwidth and number of gNBs), other KPIs such as the latency and the reliability will be more realistic due to the impact of the radio segment. In this regard, the integration with the TSN testbed described in other deliverables of this project will be also considered.

2.1.3 Wi-Fi and 5G integration through MPTCP

In industrial environments, Wi-Fi and 5G NPN can be seen as complementary RATs [3]. Though new Wi-Fi generations can reach very high data rates and low latencies under optimal conditions, traffic performance is severely degraded by distance, obstacles, mobility, and interference or contention in the ISM band. On the contrary, 5G NPN offers more stable performance, including features such as QoS guarantees, URLLC support, robust authentication and encryption, better scalability, etc. However, 5G leads to higher CAPEX and OPEX costs due to licenses, expensive equipment, and management complexity, while Wi-Fi has been successfully integrated in Industry 5.0 due to its low cost and its simplicity. Nevertheless, as analysed in [3], in some scenarios none of both technologies are able to provide the requested KPIS, requiring of multi-RAT connectivity solutions to match or overcome Ethernet performance.

The integration of 5G and Wi-Fi, or 5G and non-3GPP technologies, has been addressed from the very beginning by 3GPP, including it already in Release 15 [27]. Two main types of access are specified, trusted and untrusted, which require of specific 5G Core NFs to enable the Wi-Fi UE traffic to be routed through the UPF. Additionally, the 3GPP specified the access traffic steering, splitting, and switching (AT3S) framework in Release 16 [28]. This functionality permits to aggregate the protocol data unit (PDU) sessions that a UE maintains through different access networks, allowing to split data flows through several RATs. The concrete implementation of the AT3S steering function is not defined, allowing different options including Multi-Path TCP (MPTCP).

MPTCP allows a single TCP connection to utilize multiple network paths simultaneously. This enables to improve the performance of the connection by distributing data across different paths, which can include different network interfaces, such as 5G and Wi-Fi. MPTCP allows to implement redundancy, load balancing and aggregation capabilities, which affect the reliability, the latency and the throughput performance of the flows. Since TCP is the common protocol used in industrial applications, MPTCP has emerged as a relevant solution to provide multi-RAT connectivity in these scenarios [29].

2.1.3.1 State of the art

As stated in [30], the main objectives of MPTCP are:

- A single connection should be able to use multiple network paths.
- Performance through each path must be equal to regular TCP and without starving it.
- Existing applications must be able to use MPTCP.
- MPTCP must not impact connectivity on a path where regular TCP works.

Figure 3-8: MPTCP in the TCP/IP stack.

Note that in order to use MPTCP, both communication ends need to implement the protocol [30]. However, although an open-source implementation for the Linux Kernel is available¹⁴, nowadays its support is still not universal. However, solutions such as the utilization of a MPTCP proxy can be used to support the use of MPTCP session between an MPTCP host and a TCP host [28], as shown in Figure 3-9.

Figure 3-9: MPTCP proxy utilisation [28].

In the case of 5G networks, the MPTCP proxy can be placed after the UPF component, for instance in the same edge server. Additionally, in industrial scenarios, multi-RAT Linux-based Customer Premises Equipment (CPE) supporting MPTCP might be used in order to enable MPTCP at the UE side [3].

Although multipath operation may enhance the performance of the traffic flows, several challenges arise [31][32]. Optimal multipath operation should have a perfect knowledge of the networks characteristics (e.g., bandwidth, delay, packet error rate) to prevent head-of-line blocking problems and minimize the buffer occupancy. However, this knowledge is complex to achieve in real scenarios, especially in wireless networks. Additionally, the heterogeneity of the RATs can lead to highly asymmetric paths, in terms of capacity or delay, what may impact the order of data delivery in the communications ends, degrading TCP performance. Indeed, as evaluated in [31], in some cases MPTCP could provide lower goodput than TCP.

In order to improve MPTCP performance, research has mainly focused on the MPTCP scheduler. As show in Figure 3-10 [32], the MPTCP scheduler decides how the TCP data is sent through the TCP flows. This decision has a direct impact on traffic performance,

¹⁴ <https://multipath-tcp.org/>

allowing to apply policies devoted to increases reliability or throughput, decrease latency, or implement load balancing, among others.

Figure 3-10: MPTCP architecture and operations of the scheduler [32].

The Linux MPTCP implementation incorporates three different schedulers, minRTT, redundant and round-robin, which are described as follows [32]:

- By default, it uses minRTT, which schedules packets to the subflow with the lowest Round-Trip Time (RTT) among the flows that are not limited by the congestion window (CWND). This approach tends to use all the available subflows according to the status of the CWND of each flow and trying to avoid head-of-line blocking situations.
- On the other hand, the redundant approach sends TCP segments on all available flows. This limits the total throughput according to the path with smallest maximum throughput and decreases efficiency. However, it provides low latency and high reliability.
- Finally, the round-robin approach selects one available subflow after the other when assigning segments, without monitoring its performance (e.g., the RTT). During bulk transfers, where the send queue is backlogged, it stops performing in a round-robin manner and selects the flows according to their availability (i.e., reception of ACKs). Some implementations allow to configure the number of consecutive packets to be sent per flow.

Other scheduler approaches have been proposed in the state-of-the-art, focusing on different use cases and optimization targets [32]. ECF (Earliest Completion First) solution tries to find and use the fastest paths, considering the RTT, the CWND and the size of send buffers. In case the fastest paths are not available, it computes if waiting for them to become available will give better performance than using an available but slower path. QAware monitors the occupancy of the Network Interface Cards (NICs) and the RTT of the paths aiming at increasing the overall throughput. MuSher consider dual Wi-Fi devices, using 802.11ad and 802.11ac, which lead to heterogeneous paths (faster but less reliable vs slower but more reliable). MuSher implements mechanisms to adapt the scheduler to wireless link variations, trying to match the expected wireless throughput in

each interface. BLEST (blocking estimation) and STFT (shortest transfer time first) aim at providing low latency. BLEST is designed to estimate and minimise transfer blocking, by deciding whether to send over slower subflows or not. On the other hand, STFT tries to predict the transfer time of a segment according to the characteristic of all the subflows, mainly their congestion state (i.e., whether the subflow is in slow-start or congestion avoidance, and the number of segments already queued in the subflow).

2.1.3.2 Initial design

The initial design of the 6GSMART solution will rely on the integration of Wi-Fi 6 and 5G NR networks through MPTCP, using as building blocks the MPTCP CPE and proxy elements. As introduced in the previous section, the MPTCP scheduler permits different configurations or implementations, e.g., round-robin and redundant, which may require of different MPTCP CPE and proxy deployments. Thus, we can envision an MPTCP architecture where different end-to-end slices are deployed and contain different MPTCP realizations, according to the service or application requirements. Figure 3-11 illustrates this concept.

Figure 3-11: MPTCP solution design.

The selection of UPF is managed by the SMF and could be based on the Data Network Name (DNN) or on the Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (S-NSSAI) value. In this latter case, the slice selection will be managed by the Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF). These functionalities are supported by the Open5Gs 5G Core, introduced in Section 2.1.2.1.

According to this architecture, we will analyse the performance of different MPTCP schedulers and their impact on KPIs, mainly in relation to URLLC service category. Special focus will be placed on analysing the asymmetry of 5G and Wi-Fi RANs under different conditions. While using Wi-Fi 6 we can reach bandwidths of 80 or 160 MHz, in our 5G indoor network we will have a limitation of 40 MHz. However, under interference, congestion or mobility conditions, this asymmetric relationship may change. Additionally, mechanisms related to QoS assurance (e.g., 5G QoS bearers or Wi-Fi QoS) may also impact it.

Finally, note that the developments within this task will have a strong relationship with the work developed by the partner in charge of task “6GSMART-EZ: 6G URLLC through Multi-WAT”, since we expect to integrate our solution with their Multi-RAT/Multi-WAT deployment. Additionally, final KPI requirements will come from 6GSMART-S and 6GSMART-EXP subprojects. Finally, in the 6GSMART-EZ tasks related to Zero-Touch automation, we plan to study and implement solutions to facilitate the deployment of this MPTCP solution in industrial environments.

2.2 5GNR-based localisation of AVGs

In recent years, the advancement of technology has led to significant improvements in various industries, particularly in the realm of automation. One such technological evolution is the emergence of Automated Guided Vehicles, (AGVs) in industrial settings. AGVs are vehicles equipped with navigational systems that enable them to move and perform tasks autonomously within industrial environments. These vehicles have proven to be invaluable assets in enhancing efficiency, productivity, and safety in manufacturing and logistics operations. However, several challenges persist, particularly in tracking and estimating the positions of AGVs within industrial facilities [33].

Ensuring precise tracking and estimation of AGV positions is crucial for optimizing their operations, but factors such as environmental variations, obstacles, and sensor limitations can introduce errors in position estimation, leading to inefficiencies and potential safety hazards. Therefore, this section presents the state of the art and the initial design of the 6GSMART solution to track and estimate the positions of AGVs in industrial environments.

2.2.1 State of the art

The increasing integration of automated vehicles and advanced technologies in industrial environments proves challenging due to their deployment in dynamic scenarios, underscoring the urgent requirement for high-precise localization.

The management and tracking of AGV positions have relied on optical solutions such as cameras and ranging sensors like LiDAR, thus introducing enough levels of accuracy and reliability [34]. Nonetheless, incorporating LiDAR into each AGV proves to be highly expensive and impractical for most applications. Moreover, cameras necessitate significant computational power to process the images and are normally not enough to provide a precise position in dense areas, as can be the case in industrial environments. To summarize, alternative non-optical methods such as Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), Wi-Fi, Ultra-Wideband (UWB), and cellular networks can complement the existing optical approaches in order to increase the tracking device precision.

GNSS is known for achieving centimeter-level accuracy and is predominantly employed in outdoor scenarios [35]. However, the effectiveness of GNSS heavily relies on satellite configuration and visibility, rendering it susceptible to challenges like signal interferences, reflections, and weak signal reception in densely populated urban areas and indoor scenarios. Consequently, when GNSS fails, diverse alternative localization techniques, as mentioned earlier, can be implemented, or even coexist.

Wi-Fi technology operates on 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz radio frequencies within a range of about 50-100m. Wi-Fi localization based on the fingerprinting method [36] introduces accurate location and does not require Line-of-Sight (LoS) measurements of Access Points (AP) within indoor environments. However, this technology suffers from the computational complexity of collaborative localization as well as synchronization latency due to the mobility of the AGVs. Furthermore, in industrial environments, other technologies such as 5G New Radio (5G-NR), have proven to be more efficient than Wi-Fi in terms of latency and reliability requirements [37], thus putting this technology aside.

UWB is a cutting-edge radio technology used to transmit data over short distances with high bandwidth (about 500MHz), that operates at a frequency range from 3.1 to 10.6 GHz and utilizes a small amount of power. UWB low-cost technology has short coverage and is particularly suitable in indoor spaces. It also introduces high-precision localization with centimeter-level accuracy and resistance to interference. Nevertheless, UWB technology deployment is based on more than three sensors that cover a specific area, and out of the intersection of center regions of all sensors, the signal coverage is notoriously affected [38].

Finally, 5G-NR networks, enabled by higher carrier frequencies, wider signal bandwidths, frame flexibility, and massive MIMO technologies, offer new opportunities for enhanced localization services. In fact, a single cellular-based low-cost solution for tracking and estimating the AGV positions can be implemented using this technology. In 5G-NR a flexible waveform and frame size is introduced, enabling low latency and improved reliability in addition to high data applications. Such flexibility is achieved by supporting the coexistence of multiple numerologies that define the frame and the structure of the waveform.

2.2.2 Initial design

To tackle the challenges mentioned earlier, the proposal suggests the implementation of a 5G-NR single-based cellular solution. Several steps have been taken to implement and develop the proposed solution to effectively track and estimate the positions of AGVs.

The objective is the development of a highly precise wireless localization system. This proposed methodology involves the creation of a singular AGV cellular-based localization framework tailored to 5G-NR systems. To accomplish this, our localization framework implements advanced signal processing algorithms to extract the angle and distance information from the received signals transmitted between the base station and the AGVs [39].

The proposed first design of the solution is illustrated in Figure 3-12, which presents an initial visual representation of the proposed system.

Figure 3-12: 6GSMART AVG localization solution - Initial design.

As our goal is to estimate the position of an AGV, denoted as, $p_{AGV} = (x_{AGV}, y_{AGV})$ where p_{AGV} denotes the AGV position and x_{AGV} , and y_{AGV} represents the 2D coordinates of its position. This approach entails sending a reference signal information from the AGV to the Base Station, (BS), as depicted in the first block of Figure 3-12. By employing this technique, we are able to estimate the channel between both devices as the transmitted reference signal is also known at the receiver. A reference signal is used for decoding the UL/DL Shared Channel (PD/USCH) and can be transmitted either in uplink or downlink directions, uplink being the chosen direction in our case [40]. Moreover, the reference signals are valuable in scenarios involving high mobility allowing for increased data rate transmission rates and facilitating the tracking of rapid changes in the channel. Additionally, the strategic placement of these signals within a time slot makes them particularly well-suited for low-latency applications, as encountered in industrial environments.

In wireless communications systems, estimating the distance between transmitter and receiver is crucial for various applications, including localization in industrial settings. One common method for distance estimation is based on calculating the Time of Flight (ToF) of transmitted signals. In this section, we investigate the principle behind ToF-based distance estimation and its applications in determining the distance between an AGV and a BS in an industrial environment.

Distance Estimator:

Distance estimation relies on measuring the time taken by a signal to travel from the transmitter (AGV) to the receiver (BS). In our implementation, we utilize a specific signal, known as Demodulation Reference Signals (DMRS) for ToF calculations. These signals denoted as $DMRS_{TX}$, and $DMRS_{RX}$ which lies in their auto-correlation properties, particularly their belonging to the family of constant amplitude zero autocorrelation (CAZAC) sequences [41].

This allows us to accurately determine the distance by analyzing the correlation between the transmitted and received signals. More specifically, the cross-correlation function, (CCF), ($R_{xy}(t)$) is defined as the integral of the product of the transmitted signal, $x(\tau)$ and the received signal $y(t + \tau)$ overall time shifts τ . This expression can be stated as:

$$R_{xy}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(\tau) \cdot y(t + \tau) d\tau$$

Next, we analyse the CCF to identify the peaks corresponding to significant correlations between the transmitted and received signals. These peaks represent instances where the received signal aligns well with the transmitted signal, indicating a potential match. Therefore, the position of the peak in the CCF indicates the time delay (Δt) between the AGV and the BS signals, which directly corresponds to the time of flight. Hence, the distance can be calculated using this formula:

$$\hat{d} = \Delta t \cdot c$$

where \hat{d} is the distance between the AGV and BS Δt is the time of flight of the signal and c is the speed of the light in the medium.

Angles estimator:

In this subsection, we delve into the detailed explanation of the estimator for the Angle of Arrival (AoA) of the AGV, defined as $(\hat{\theta})$. Similar to the distance estimator, the AoA, utilizes the transmitted and received DMRS signals to estimate the direction.

$$H(f) = \frac{S(f)}{R(f)}$$

where, $H(f)$ is the channel response at a given frequency f . The function $R(f)$ is the received DMRS in the frequency domain, whereas $S(f)$ is the transmitted DMRS sequence. The ratio of $R(f)$ to $S(f)$ give us an estimation of the channel's response at that frequency. This assumes that the channel is linear and time-invariant, which means that the properties of the channel do not change throughout observation.

The first step in the AoA estimation process involves evaluating the channel between the AGV and the BS using the DMRS sequences in the frequency domain. This is accomplished by processing the DMRS sequences within the frequency domain. This evaluation enables the construction of the Channel State Information (CSI) matrix, which is crucial for estimating the AoA of the signal.

The CSI matrix is constructed using the estimated channel responses $H(f)$ across all subcarriers and antennas. More specifically, the CSI provides a comprehensive representation of the channel characteristics across the entire frequency spectrum and across all antennas. However, this estimation may include multiple wavefronts from different directions, potentially complicating AoA estimation.

To address these complexities, we implement the Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) algorithm. MUSIC is a powerful algorithm used for direction-of-arrival estimation array signal processing applications [42]. By analysing the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the CSI matrix, MUSIC can effectively estimate the angles of arrival, even in the presence of interference or multipath propagation.

Within the CSI matrix, each received antenna and subcarrier is associated with a complex number. To pinpoint the most pronounced AoA from this matrix, we engage the MUSIC algorithm. MUSIC operates by exploiting the orthogonality between the signal and noise subspaces, which are ascertained via the decomposition of the covariance matrix derived from the received signals. The music function can be expressed as,

$$P(\theta) = \frac{1}{a^H(\theta)E_nE_n^H a(\theta)}$$

, where $P(\theta)$ represents the MUSIC spatial spectrum for a given angle θ . The vector $a(\theta)$ is the steering vector, which describes how the wavefront from a signal arriving at angle θ adds coherently across the array of antennas. The term $a^H(\theta)$ is the Hermitian transpose (conjugate transpose) of $a(\theta)$. The matrix E_n contains the eigenvectors of the noise subspace, obtained from the eigenvalue decomposition of the CSI matrix. The noise subspace is orthogonal to the signal subspace, and by scanning through all possible angles θ , the MUSIC algorithm identifies the peaks in $P(\theta)$ that correspond to the estimated angles of arrival.

The MUSIC algorithm exploits the fact that the steering vectors corresponding to the true angles of arrival will be orthogonal to the noise subspace, resulting in high peaks in the spatial spectrum.

We can summarize it as the AoA is ascertained by scanning the entire steering vector matrix to isolate those steering vectors that are precisely orthogonal. The MUSIC algorithm's prowess lies in its ability to distinguish between these orthogonal vectors, facilitating the determination of the strongest AoA amidst a multitude of signals. Thus, by applying the MUSIC algorithm to the CSI matrix, we can accurately determine the AoA, thereby significantly enhancing the AGV's position estimation accuracy.

Positioning:

Subsequently, the third block of Figure 3-12 combines the angle and distance estimated to compute the AGV position, p_{AGV} . To go further, in order to obtain the estimated position, we take as reference the position of the BS defined as, $p_{BS} = (x_{BS}, y_{BS})$ in conjunction with the distance, (\hat{d}), and angle, ($\hat{\theta}$) estimated value from the channel. Hence, we can elaborate on the AGV position in detail, defined as:

$$\hat{p}_{AGV} = (x_{AGV}, y_{AGV}) = (x_{BS} + \hat{d} \cdot \cos(\hat{\theta}), y_{BS} + \hat{d} \cdot \sin(\hat{\theta}))$$

The AGV localization KPIs evaluate the accuracy and efficiency of the AVG localization framework within the factory environment. We primarily focus on estimating the AGV location in the factory space, enabling effective coordination and optimization of their operational tasks. Additionally, we measure the errors in AGV localization, facilitating the positioning error during a window time, and also the cumulative distribution of the positioning error. Therefore, we will use the following metrics to evaluate our KPIs, which are divided into 2 different categories:

- I. Positioning Accuracy Metrics:
 - a. Positioning error in AGV localization during specific time windows across the factory floor.
 - b. Cumulative distribution of AGV positioning errors across different operational periods.
- II. Environmental Robustness Indicators:
 - a. Evaluation of AGV localization performance under varying environmental conditions (e.g., lighting, obstacles)

4. Conclusions

Industrial applications impose specific and strong requirements which are challenging to accomplish by wireless networks. In recent years, the massive worldwide adoption of Wi-Fi and IoT has also impacted the network infrastructure in industrial environments. Compared to wired networks, wireless brings interesting benefits such as reducing CAPEX and OPEX costs due to deployment and maintenance, enabling mobility or seamlessly increasing the device density. However, Wi-Fi networks are not reliable enough to provide industrial services with the required QoS guarantees. 5G has opened the door to the deployment of NPN networks in the industry, which allow to obtain the benefits and novelties of 5G NR and Core while maintaining the private control of the network infrastructure and the data.

In this deliverable we have introduced the main 5G, BY5 and 6G KPIs of interest to Industry 5.0, together with significant solutions to provide them. Particularly, the focus of i2CAT is placed on four main solutions: (i) Wi-Fi MAC mechanisms to enable wireless Time Sensitive Networking (TSN), (ii) High-performance 5G Core User Plane Function (UPF), (iii) Wi-Fi and 5G integration through MultiPath Transport Control Protocol (MPTCP), and (iv) 5G NR-based localisation of AVGs. For each of the proposed solutions, which cover different use cases and technologies, we have presented relevant state of the art and an initial design.

Together with the outputs of the different partners involved in this subproject, and the requirements coming from 6GSMART-S subproject, this deliverable will serve as basis to guide the developments towards the final solution to be implemented and evaluated within the context of this project and to be integrated in the demonstrators and PoCs of the 6GSMART-EXP subproject.

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